

INTRODUCTION OF A PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY FOR THE PRE-ASSEMBLY OF MULTI-MATERIAL-PREFORMS AIMING AT A LARGE SCALE PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

In recent times, conventional lightweight construction strategies in the automotive production are enriched by new material combinations, such as fiber reinforced structures. New technologies arise and open further potential in lightweight design. Many production processes, that go along with these technologies demand for multi-material preforms as pre-product. The Institute of Machine Tools and Production Technology (IWF) and the Institute of Joining and Welding (ifs) of the Technische Universität Braunschweig do research on production technologies for multi-material respectively hybrid lightweight components.

In these activities different types of materials with specific properties are joined to one part. So, a functionalization of the whole part is achieved. The approach of the hybrid lightweight design is accompanied by the necessity of developing appropriate production technologies. These are required to empower an efficient and automated manufacturing of complex geometries in hybrid lightweight design.

The presented work bases on the manufacturing of fiber-reinforced thermoplastic-metal-hybrid parts using hybrid preforms. It aims on the combination of large scale processes of metallic manufacturing with the lightweight potential of fiber reinforced plastics. These preforms are built up from semi-finished parts in a pre-assembling process. This article describes results of the BMBF funded project ProVor, namely the whole development process of a first demonstrator built-up, which depicts the feasibility of an automated pre-assembly approach for hybrid preforms in the scenario of a large scale production scenario. The development process starts with the workout of different production scenarios. Out of this, required functionalities are deduced. Afterwards different concepts of functionally integrated handling and joining tools are developed and compared. Finally an experimental set-up consisting of a robot with a demonstrator of an integrated handling and joining device is built up and tested.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the large scale production of metallic lightweight components for the automotive industry, mostly optimized production processes of molding and forming technologies are well-established. These processes use materials with a high availability, allow short cycle times and a high degree of automation. In contrast, the implementation of fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) despite of intensive research stays out in middle- and high-volume production, yet. Considering the high material costs and the not mass production-ready processes, FRP is applied only in small quantity in premium segment [1, 2]. Thus, for example the Resin Transfer Molding (RTM), is limited due to long injection and resin curing times.

High material and manufacturing costs of pure FRP constructions lead to non economical

components. This is why, there are attempts to combine metallic and FRP components, with the aim to cut down costs and to get the best of both worlds. The results are components which are designed in a multi-material-mix. One option to produce suchlike components is to manufacture particular parts made of steel, light metal and FRP separately. For each part material-specific production technologies are used. Afterwards, the parts are joined during a final assembly by adhesives or mechanical joining techniques. These joints lead to further production steps, additional material and an impairment of structural behavior. This is inconsistent with the lightweight approach.

In contrast, component-integrated hybridization fully uses the potential of the FRP-based lightweight design. This requires another approach in terms of production technology [3]. In this approach, different types of materials with specific properties are integrated in a component at once. So, a functionalization (e.g. mechanical or thermal) of the whole component is achieved in combination of all parts, without a subsequent joining process.

Due to the mostly conventional material-specific orientated plant concepts, an economical manufacturing of hybrid components in high lot sizes is not feasible. New technologies have to expand the conventional material-specific orientated concepts and ensure a high degree of automation [3]. The objective of recent work at Technische Universität Braunschweig is to combine the large scale processes of metallic manufacturing and the lightweight potential of FRP.

A promising technology of manufacturing lightweight parts in high lot sizes can be found in molding or forming processes based on thermoforming and injection molding of thermoplastics [4]. A great potential to cut down cycle time is generated by the use of pre-impregnated fabrics with a thermoplastic matrix and metallic inlays. This is due to the fact that there is no need of resin injection and curing times.

The cycle-time of the forming tool primarily depends on the material supply respectively the time of placing several parts into the mold. Placing several thermoplastic fabrics and metallic parts into the mold leads to long opening times of the tool and consequently to long cycle-times. To attain large scale cycle-times, the complexity of positioning several cuttings has to be moved into upstream processes to reduce non-productive times of the tool.

Figure 1: Concept of a process chain for the manufacturing of hybrid components. The work in this article described, focuses on the pre-assembly of hybrid preforms (marked process steps)

This article describes the approach by the IWF and ifs that is concerned with the findings above. It aims at the manufacturing of hybrid semi-finished parts detached from the final production process step in e.g. a forming tool. These parts have the properties and functions of the subsequent component, e.g. load-adapted fiber orientation. The build-up of these hybrid preforms is realized in a pre-assembly process. The hybrid preforms are manufactured by the combination of simple semi-finished FRP and metal parts. They build the basic structure of the finally manufactured component. The cycle time of the pre-assembly is synchronized with the cycle time of the downstream process. Afterwards, the preform is transferred into a forming or molding process to create the final geometry, strength and quality of the structural part. The concept of this process chain is shown in Figure 1.

The described pre-assembling approach aims at a high reduction of non-productive times of the forming tool. A pre-assembled hybrid preform allows for a shorter opening time of the tool, instead of

placing several cuttings into the mold. Moreover, the automated assembly of the cuttings is easier beyond the forming tool because of less limitations of working space.

2 APPROACHES OF PRE-ASSEMBLY IN LIGHTWEIGHT PRODUCTION

The approach of pre-assembling several semi-finished parts to a preform bases on composite manufacturing processes like Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) and automated lay-up of tailored blanks for thermoplastforming, like introduced in [5–8]. In the RTM process a near-net-shape preform is built-up by draping several layers of dry, limp fiber patches into a mold. By means of heating and pressing, the layers are joined. The joined layers form a near-net-shape preform, which offers sufficient strength for further handling operations. Afterwards, the preform is transferred into a molding tool and injected by resin to consolidate the fabric [7]. After curing, the component has its final strength. Also in the process chain in [5, 6, 8], several layers or parts of fiber tapes are applied onto a tooling surface and are fused by hot forming. The fabricated blank is transferred into subsequent processes. Instead of dry fabrics, these processes use fabrics with pre-impregnated thermoplastic matrix. But they do not consider the combination of fabrics and metallic parts.

The conventional manufacturing of preforms and composite parts is characterized by a high amount of manual operations. Hence, there are approaches to automate several process steps. Exemplary approaches are functionally integrated tools, which combine handling, draping und heating operations [9–13]. These tools show attempts to parallelize two or more process steps. This results into shorter cycle times.

Within the scope of the RTM process chain, these automation concepts show high impact on the reduction of non-productive times and manual production steps. The long curing times during the consolidation process allow long cycle-times for the preforming process (≥ 10 min.). But, considering the aim of using large scale production technologies based on metallic processes, cycle-times have to be much shorter [9]. Thus, the automation approaches as described above have to be adjusted to the requirements of the intended pre-assembly process for hybrid preforms by the IWF and the ifs. Further, an adjustment of the tool functionalities concerning the desired processes is necessary.

3 CONCEPTS FOR AN AUTOMATED PRE-ASSEMBLING PROCESS OF MULTI-MATERIAL-PREFORMS

Before mentioned findings triggered investigations in the field of process design for economic lightweight production. First investigations on this topic were made by the IWF and ifs within the one-year-long project ProVor. The project ProVor was funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research. It was one of three initial projects during the preliminary phase of the ForschungsCampus “Open Hybrid LabFactory e.V.” (OHLF). Within the scope of OHLF, researchers and industrial partners develop innovative production technologies for high-volume hybrid lightweight production.

The following section describes a method and first results of research activities. The presented work focuses on first feasibility tests. These tests provide the base for the development of a comprehensive concept for an automated pre-assembling process. They serve as exploratory work for the follow-on project ProVor^{Plus}. ProVor^{Plus} extends the pre-assembly by the subsequent final production step, see Figure 1. The objective of the four-year-long project ProVorPlus is to investigate the entire process chain of the approach described in section 1.

Figure 2 presents the methodological approach for the development of the introduced pre-assembly process: Initially different production scenarios were worked out. On the basis of the scenarios sub-processes were identified, which are needed during the pre-assembly. Out of this, the required functionalities were deduced and geometries of specimens for the feasibility tests were defined. Afterwards, concepts for the implementation of the gathered requirements into hardware were developed. Finally, one concept was built up in form of a demonstrator.

Figure 2: Methodological approach for development of a preassembly process

3.1 Production scenarios and required functionalities

The development of scenarios and concepts lead to better overview of the pre-assembly approach and the requirements of this production technology. [14] introduces these scenarios and describes them in detail. An overview on these scenarios is given in Figure 4.

All pre-assembling scenarios have the same interface to upstream processes. The input of the pre-assembling process is the material supply. The interface to downstream processes differs. Each scenario is connected to a final pressing process. This final production step of forming or pressing determines the cycle time for all preceding process steps.

Figure 3: Three main production scenarios to identify required functionalities for the manufacturing hybrid preforms in mass production processes

In scenario (S1), the pre-assembly is decoupled from the subsequent forming process by a buffer. Tailored semi-finished parts are combined by repeating handling and joining processes. The manufactured preform is transported into a stock or buffer. Afterwards, the forming process can be supplied out of the stock.

In scenario (S2), the manufactured preform is placed into an external oven to be heated and melted for the subsequent forming process. The hot and limp preform is placed into the forming tool. In this scenario, taking the heated preform out of the oven is not part of the pre-assembly.

In scenario (S3), the preform is heated during the transportation step and placed directly into the forming tool. In terms of a mass production this is the most promising and most efficient scenario.

By means of these three scenarios, five functionalities, that have to be realized by an appropriate production technology, can be deduced:

- gripping of semi finished materials with different properties (e.g. tailored organo sheets, formed metallic inlays)
- placing and joining the semi-finished parts to a manageable preform
- pre-heating the preform for the subsequent forming process
- transporting and placing the preform into the forming tool within the cycle-time of the press

These functionalities can be summarized into three main functionalities: *handling, joining and heating*. Handling includes gripping, placing and transporting. These functionalities have to be considered for the further process and hardware design.

For feasibility tests, a reference geometry for specimens according to DIN EN 1465 was chosen. Also a material combination was defined. The dimensions of the tailored parts measure 25 mm x 100 mm. The joining area measures 12,5 mm x 25 mm ($A=312,5 \text{ mm}^2$). The metal adherend (1st part of

the specimen) is for example steels with high strength (DC01). The plastic adherend (2nd part of the specimen) consists of glass fiber reinforced polyamide 6.

Another very important requirement forms the need of handling the preform between the process steps. In these terms the achievable joining strength is highly important. The required joining strength is not as high as in the final component, but it has to be a sufficient strength for handling operations while transferring the preform into a stock, oven or the forming tool. Several parts of the preform have to stay oriented during the handling processes. In context of these investigations the required strength is achieved, if a force of 1 to 2 MPa can be transferred onto the joining area.

Figure 4: Specimens according to DIN EN 1465 (dimensions in mm); specification of area for fusion bonding with required joining force F

Within the project, fusion bonding was chosen as joining technique. Using this technique, the thermoplastic matrix melts in the contact area to the metallic part and generates a joint after solidifying under pressure (F) (Figure 4) [15]. The ifs investigated this technique by heating the samples with a hot tool (L) [14]. To get such a joining connection, a joining pressure of about 0,5 MPa is required [16]. For a joining area of 312.5 mm², the joining tool has to transfer a force of 160 N onto the contact area. The aim is to generate the required force independent of the used robotic hardware.

Requirements related to specific gripping concepts were not considered in ProVor. The Challenges of gripping materials with different properties (cold, hot, solid and limp) will be researched in ProVor^{Plus}.

3.2 Concepts for integrated handling and joining tools

Referring to the presented production scenarios and the defined requirements and assumptions, different hardware concepts were worked out (Figure 6) [14]. They contain the identified functionalities and cover most of the described scenarios presented in section 3.1.

Figure 5: Three basic concepts for a production technology for the pre-assembly of multi-material preforms

Concept C1 is designed to carry out handling and joining operations by two separate tools that are mounted as end-effectors at industrial robots. Both robots work separately. Gripping and joining components are attached on a base frame. Their position on the frame is variable. So, it is feasible to adapt different part geometries. The required process forces for joining are generated by the robot, an

external or gripper-integrated pressing unit (independence of the used robot). The force is transferred by the joining component.

Concept C2 combines gripping and joining components into one tool. Both functions are separated by the use of a double-sided tool. This concept does not allow parallel gripping and joining.

Concept C3 combines the components for gripping and joining on one side of the tool. This enables a parallel gripping and joining of parts. Compared with concept C1, multiple alignment operations of parts are not required anymore. This advantage has a high potential of reducing non-productive times. It meets the requirement of short cycle-times.

The presented concepts C1 to C3 are designed to fulfill the requirements of the described scenarios S1 to S2. There is already preliminary work carried out, with the aim of developing further concepts, which integrates functionalities and fulfill the requirements of scenario S3 (e.g. the handling of limp material and heating) [12, 17–19].

As mentioned before, an external pressing unit is required, that works along with the handling and joining concepts. It is needed to generate the required joining forces independent from the used robot system. The pressing unit ensures that the parts are pressed together in their joining area while they are heated via an induction device. Table 1 shows considered solutions for the development of the pressing unit:

Function	Solution 1	Solution 2	Solution 3
Allocation of force	 <i>gripper integrated</i>		
Force transition	 <i>knee-lever</i>		
force generation	 <i>pneumatical</i>		
force control	 <i>path-controlled</i>		

Table 1: Considered solutions for the development of a pressing unit

These solutions provide a great design freedom for the desired demonstrator and the planned feasibility test. An evaluation process figured out the most promising combination: tool concept C3 with an external pressing unit that is pneumatically actuated and equipped with solutions for both, force- and path-control. In several steps, the components and interfaces of the tool and the pressing

unit were set. The use of standard components was preferred. This will ensure the up-scaling from the experimental set-up to larger part geometries in later works.

Figure 6 depicts the final concept for the experimental set-up with pressing unit and functionally integrated gripping and joining tool. The set-up uses an external frame to support the robot during the joining process. The dimensions of the set-up are initially orientated towards the geometry of the defined specimens in section 3.1. It consists of the following components:

1. external frame
2. tool changer: interface of industrial robot and tool
3. functional integrated tool with gripping devices (a) and joining units (b)
4. semi-finished parts (sample cuttings of metal and FRP)
5. swing clamp cylinders for the generation of joining force, attached to the base frame
6. force sensors for controlling the process: in the joining units and in the base
7. table with stack for the cuttings/specimens: main workspace of the demonstrator

Figure 6: Concept for an experimental set-up: integrated handling and joining tool with an external pressing unit

3.3 Functional demonstrator

The described experimental set-up was built up to perform first feasibility tests of the desired pre-assembly process, based on scenario S1 and concept C3. Figure 7 shows the set-up of the developed gripping and joining tool. The gripping devices (heat resistant vacuum grippers) and joining units (inductor with an integrated compression die) are attached to a base frame. The base frame supplies the connection to the robot and transfers the process forces generated by the external pressing unit.

Figure 7 also depicts the external pressing unit. The lateral mounted swing clamp cylinders press onto the base frame of the tool during the joining process. The pressing process is force-controlled by means of a pressure control. Force sensors are mounted between the inductor and the base frame of the tool and below the table of the pressing unit, see also Figure 6. They are connected to a programmable controller that regulates a valve. The chosen hardware is designed for joining forces of 200 N.

Figure 7: Functional integrated handling device with gripping devices and heating units (left) and external pressing unit (middle, right)

After constructing the general experimental set-up, it was implemented into a robot cell, see Figure 8. This environment consists of an industrial robot (1) which operates the functionally integrated gripping and joining tool, a tray for supplying the specimens (2), the pressing unit (3) in the main workspace and periphery like controllers of the robot, the inductor and the pressing unit.

Figure 8: Experimental set-up for feasibility tests

3 FEASIBILITY TESTS IN A SAMPLE PROCESS

After building up the experimental environment, feasibility test become necessary. Tests are required not only for the hardware itself, but even more for the desired large scale process, see above. To carry out first tests, a sample process was designed, see Figure 9. This sample process is structured into two sub-processes: handling and joining.

Figure 9: Sample process for feasibility tests

During the handling process cuttings are taken out of a material stock, placed at the joining workspace, see Figure 10, left. Here, the joining is carried out by fusion bonding which is investigated by the ifs [14, 20] see Figure 10, right.

Figure 10: Handling of specimens (left) and joining by fusion bonding (right) with the integrated tool

The superior robot control triggers the generation of the joining force with the external pressing unit. The process control measures the force between inductor and joining area. The measured value controls the clamp cylinders to adjust the target force. Therefore, the gripping and joining tool is decoupled of the robot by unlocking the tool changer and is pushed down by the pressing unit. The inductor heats the metallic component and the thermoplastic material melts. When joining is finished, the clamp cylinders reverse and the tool is coupled at the robot again. After joining, the specimens are transported in another handling operation to the next production step.

For the evaluation of the experimental set-up, the reliability of the generation of the joining force was investigated. The experiment cycle consists of the described sample process. The cycle starts with the tool above the joining workspace. The tool is then pressed onto the specimens by the robot with a preload force of 70 N. The clamping unit increases the force until the present target force of 200 N is reached. This cycle was repeated 50 times for each measurement cycle. In the experiments, the joining force was recorded by the integrated force sensor, located underneath the joining workspace.

The developed control loop allows the adjustment of two parameters:

1. the increment factor (k , in ms) for adjusting the increment speed of the pressure regulator control path and
2. the offset (o , in N) for adjusting the target value offset to increase the control aggressivity and to prevent slow target value convergence.

Four experiments E1 to E4 with different parameter sets were carried out. The goal was to determine valid values for both preset parameters that allow for a stable and reliable force control. Unsuitable parameters could result in overshooting the target value (eg. too aggressive control mode) or unnecessarily long cycle times (eg. too slow pressure increase). In a first run the parameter k was increased in three steps. The parameter o was fixed to a moderate level of 5 N. In these first results k with a minimal deviation of the joining force was identified. Thus, for $k = 200$ ms also o was change to 10 N. Table 2 and Figure 11 show the results: E3 reached best results for mean, maximum and standard deviation of joining force. The force curves for all experiments show quite similar behavior of the controlled pressing and joining process. This evaluation shows, that the joining force is generated reproducibly. The parameters of the control are well adjustable. Thus, a reliable and reproductive process is feasible with the worked out concept.

Table 2: Results of feasibility test for the implemented control of the pressing unit: comparison of different control parameters show a high reproducibility

Figure 11: Ten out of 50 cycles for feasibility test with the parameter set: $k = 200 \text{ N}$ and $\sigma = 10 \text{ kPa}$

Finally, the results of the researched fusion bonding [14] were implemented into the developed hardware environment. The attached inductor was taken into operation. With the implemented control of the heating parameters, specimens of joint FRP and metallic parts can be produced. Figure 12 shows the final product of the pre-assembly process.

Figure 12: Specimens after the feasibility tests: joint FRP and metal

3 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The present paper deals with the necessity of appropriate production technologies for implementing the hybrid lightweight approach into a large scale production. Therefore, the intended proposal was described, in which fiber reinforced thermoplastics and metallic inlays are combined during a pre-assembly-process. This process manufactures a hybrid preform. Afterwards, this preform is transferred into a forming process to manufacture the final part. For the implementation of the pre-assembling approach, different production scenarios were worked out and requirements were defined. Out of this, different concepts and processes were developed. By means of this knowledge an experimental set-up has been built. This demonstrator provides a hardware environment for the implementation of a joining technique. For feasibility tests, an inductor was taken into operation and former results of investigations on the joining process itself (carried out by ifs) were validated. In an automated sample process, first specimens of metal and FRP were joint to show the operational capability of the tested production technology.

The presented investigations are on a conceptual level. So far, the developed set-up is inflexible respecting variants of part geometries. Furthermore, the used robot and the pressing unit lead to restricted agility. Here, further investigations will be made, which obtain a higher flexibility. In future investigations, the system boundaries are extended and the subsequently forming process is also investigated. These investigations will take place in the follow-on project ProVor^{Plus}.

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